

Identity Service: A Future Service for Collecting, Storing, and Communicating Personal Identity through Wearable Interfaces

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Abstract:

Identity Service is a future service that allows users to store, collect and share Identity related information through wearable digital interfaces while on the move. Identity Service is an Interaction Design research project in the field of Service Design and Wearable Computing that aims to provide more intimate personal communication tools and analyze the effect that technologies have on socio-cultural dynamics. Identity Service provides a model for how to build new communication and human networking tools.

Keywords: Identity, Ubiquitous Computing, Human Networks, Wearable Digital Interfaces, Human-Human Interaction, Telecommunication.

Website: <http://www.identityservice.biz/ID.html> for images and video scenarios of the Identity Service.

Introduction

We are moving from the age of owning goods to the age of knowing (having access to information). Our Identity is built on information and this situation raises the concept of Identity to a new level of interest in our society. This year Identity thieves deprived more than 9 million people of their money by stealing credit cards and financial information; the consequences of which may affect people's image, role, relationships and credibility. Our Identity is everywhere but never completely with us. Our bodily evidence changes every day: we wear different clothes, different hairstyle and hair color, what evidence we have that the person here and now is person who was here yesterday? (Olsen, 2002).

A guy (Fig. 1) says that the baby in the picture is him at age 1, he has memories of growing up, a retro cognition or quasi-memory of being the baby, but it doesn't apply to the baby, he couldn't possibly know it would be him (kissing a girl) at age 28. Are they not the same person then?

Probably they are but because his parents can recall memories of both of them being the same human growing up. But are memories the only place in which our Identities survive?

Figure 1, Personal identity

Our Identity is given to us not in the first person but also by the interaction with people that surround us (Deutsch, 2002). Identity is what makes us the person we are, our interests, friends, family, experiences, everyday activities, memories, emotion, ideas.

Being flexible and dynamic, Identity gets richer and changes every day, even every hour depending on the place where we are, thanks to each new experience we encounter. How can we keep track of our identity development and communicate our complexity as human beings to people that matter to us, when the time we are allowed is very short? Digital technologies allow us to exchange information about ourselves with all kinds of people. How can we easily and securely share appropriate personal information?

Our Identity is shaped also by the way the people around us perceive it. How can we be sure to be perceived how we want to? Through my research I wish to provide an answer and comment to this.

The Identity Service consists of:

A personal database, where people can upload all types of personal information, and a wearable digital interface to access, share and broadcast this information while out and about.

Figure 2, Identity Service users and partners (banks, museums, etc.) network.

The personal database is a “user’s own” database could be set up in the user’s kitchen (for example), and managed only by the user. The Identity Database Software will run on it, but the content remain property of the user.

Subscribers can decide to share or broadcast types of personal information through any type of connected device, such as a mobile phone or wearable interface. Through the wearable interface users gain access to ad-hoc identity networks created dynamically as they move through the day. If desired buildings, machines and computers could become “smart” through Bluetooth or WiFi networks, allowing a user’s identity needs to be serviced in real time in any place (Figure 2). Subscribers can also enrich their database profile with new information collected on the move, from other people.

Such a service presents its risks as well. Identity thieves will always attempt to find ways to exploit any system. This research provides a way to imagine the future of identity through the benefits as well as the problems ubiquitous identities will create.

Identity at the supermarket

We live in a world where we already distribute continuously large amounts of personal information.

Amazon.com collects our data and uses it to affect our future choices. After buying a few books, maybe a present for a friend with completely different taste than ours, Amazon will, under the guise of customer service, set up at our next visit lists of similar books to buy and places to go as selected by other thousands people with similar interests. Similar to whom? Microsoft Passport proclaimed as the identity authentication and data safe box software of the millennium, has been found guilty of sharing customers data illegally for marketing purposes. Additionally the protocol hasn't been safe from the beginning, news reported that 200 million Passport users risked to be deprived by hackers of their personal data due to a built in software flaw discovered only after 7 months after delivery (BBC News, 2003). Outside the Internet the situation doesn't get better. When purchasing a skirt at the GAP the cashier asks for your address, and the computer stores your credit card number, indefinitely in the corporation database all for the purpose of tracking customers buying patterns. But if you want to access the same data to check your purchase history you are not allowed (despite the fact that it was collected from you).

The Identity Service would be desirable because it will provide its users with direct control and benefits over the distribution of their own personal information. The distribution and acquisition of this information is at the core of the Identity Service.

Identity at the cinema

Interest in the subject of Identity has reached a new level in popular culture too. In the film *Minority Report* (Spielberg, 2002), taking place in an over-controlled 2054 Washington D.C. Steven Spielberg presents the state of the art of automated identification and tracking systems, with techno-spiders trying to read/scan everyone's retina. While on the other hand, more poetically, *Afterlife* (Kore-Eda, 2001) from Japanese director Hirokazu Kore-Eda, examines the complex symbiotic relationship between memory and altered perception of the self. Does memory define truth or is imaginative memory an interactive process that leads to a personal and relevant truth and Identity? The Identity Service provides a view about the perception of Identity between the technological dystopia of *Minority Report* and the emotional optimism of *Afterlife*.

Defining identity in technological society

This research focuses on the way we communicate our personal identities in relation to the society we are part of and how technology influences this interaction and more deeply influences how we act and who we are. For example think how the advances in telephone technology have changed our interactions: from one shared phone for a whole village to mobile phones in our pockets.

Human Identity is the product of technological, economic, and legal systems in which particular identities develop and according to which they work. (Baldine, 2002).

The world is permeated with information (Wilson, 2003): how does this information relate to our identity? Furthermore how do our means to access this information affect our interaction?

Motivation

The aim of this research is to provide insights and investigate the methodology of Wearable Computing, and Service Design, a young discipline within the field of Interaction Design.

Methodology of Service Design

Applying a User Centered Design approach during the research phase of the Identity Service design process revealed constituent properties of Individuals Identities, later called Identity Fields (described in section Design, Software and Data Structure). The Identity Fields take into account these main assumptions:

- a) Identity is constantly transforming and evolving
- b) Every single day we can assume a new identity that is informed by our subjective experiences.
- c) Identity presents us to the world as unique individuals
- d) Identity belongs to a deeper perception of us and can be misperceived by others.
- e) Identity is the unconscious (in)tangible tool we use to interact with other individuals.

From this platform the Identity Service was designed to fulfill a cultural desire for Individual Identity enhancement tools.

Human-Human Interaction

A second point demonstrated through this research is the need to move designers' attention from HCI (Human-Computer Interaction) towards what I call HHI (Human-Human Interaction). I believe that it is only between humans that communication acquires its meaning. Interaction between humans and machines occurs mainly because there is a communication need between distant humans fulfilled through machines.

Communication between a person and a machine can be typed, clicked or spoken (employing speech recognition and speech synthesis), however, machine responses will, most likely, be limited to algorithmic ones and not compelling for the human. This is because machines aren't as sophisticated or intelligent as humans to understand emotion and ambiguity. (Shedroff, 2003).

Mediating human connectedness

We can say to know a person when we know details about him or her. An anonymous user noted "this is a two way communication process: it is not enough that I know, that a person I have just met, knows information about my personal identity. Knowing that a friend have told a lot about me to a neighbor and vice versa, does not make us know each other – but one could raise the question whether it creates a foundation for which we can know each other?"

The Identity Service gives users a tool to create a foundation for knowing people we don't know yet. This foundation is based on sharing data. How the data is shared is at the core of the service. It will not be like delivering one's own personal information on a website, for someone we just met to check it out at a later time. Instead our personal data will be delivered in real time even while we speak or just walk by, providing details that might interest others to know more about who we are.

The Identity Service allows people to get to know each other in detail, while on the move, sharing Fields of Identity. Communication of personal Identity with richness of details will result in increased connectedness. Connectedness means communicating with others intimately.

Design

The Identity Service was designed applying tools like Use Scenarios and Experience Prototypes. Identity Service provides users with renewed information technology to let them collect, store, share and acquire Identity Data.

Use scenarios

Here is presented the Identity Service user scenario and a list of the Identity Service components. Design Orienting Scenarios are used in the field of Service Design to demonstrate to potential users and partners how the experience of using the service would be.

The Elevator Pitch

Three people get stuck in a skyscraper's elevator for 2 minutes (Figure 3), while having a convenience conversation two of them start to interact and talk like if they knew each other since many years earlier. How did it happen?

Angelina's Wearable Identity was Broadcasting her Cultural Identity in a previous meeting in the same building, Steven (the blond guy), customer of the Identity Service as well, was using his Wearable Identity in Listening Mode, getting to know everything about her; John, not a customer, was trying to understand which was the girl's background and really seemed he couldn't get it until Steven told him some great things about her studies. Afterwards Steven starts to Share with Angelina his Cultural Identity and she discovers he is her favorite film director, he knows she saw his movie the night before and they take off talking. John feels a little left out. Using the Wearable Identity will be like having an extended brain, thanks to which we will be able not only to acquire new knowledge but also to recall our memories and other people details.

Figure 3, Video-scenario: Angelina, Steven, and John in the elevator.

Participatory design

The Identity Service was designed through several participatory design sessions and iterations on prototypes and interfaces. In order to create a tool that could be used by anyone in any environment, the approach followed was that of User Centered Design with a team of 10 to 15 users in the multicultural environment of Interaction Design Institute Ivrea. Most members of the institute's community, were strangers to each other even after two years of close work, most of them didn't simply have time to share with others knowledge that was part of their life but not related to current projects, or without knowing that their background could have been of interest for others.

Given this need for knowing others more intimately the users have been asked to discuss their perception of personal identity, giving important indications to shape the Identity Fields and Moods. In the first week of the participatory design phase users brought their garments (Figure 4), in order to define which Identity they assume when they wear a specific and emotionally valuable item of clothing and how their behavior changes when they wear a specific garment. The identity expressed through the garments was related to the experiences that the users lived while wearing them. The garments and accessories that represented a more meaningful balance between experience and appearance were small jewels and pins,

from this starting point we were able to define the main Identity Service Protocol and the form factor of the Wearable Identity.

Figure 4, Users' garments analyzed during the participatory design session.

Design Overview

When a customer starts using the Identity Service she will fill Identity related data into the personal database called Identity Hub. As specified earlier the personal database or Identity Hub, could be set up at the user's place. This will ensure safety for the data management, and create trust in the Identity Service, which will not be able to resell the user's data to third parties.

Figure 5, Users can upload their personal information through any kind of connected device.

The Identity Service users can retrieve or upload new data, into the Identity Hub, from any country at any time and then share it in one or more of the five Identity Moods, via Identity

Protocol (the software provided by the Identity Service) enabled devices such as Laptops, Identity Mobile Phone, and Wearable Identity (Figure 5).

Software and data structure

The Identity Protocol is a Java software application that organizes the data architecture of the Identity information contained into the Identity Hub into Five Identity Fields. The Identity Data can then be retrieved and shared in one or more of the Five Identity Moods. The Identity Data transactions are protected by the Identity Filters. The Identity Protocol Software runs on Identity compatible hardware (Identity Mobile Phones, Laptops, or Wearable Identity), making the information contained in the Identity Hub accessible by any platform.

Identity Hub (database)

Imagine the Identity Hub as an airport where information can land, can stay forever and become citizen of our Identity or take off again after a few hours without coming back. The user's Identity Hub keeps on growing constantly and automatically because of the amount of data users encounter and receive everyday. The Identity Hub is kept safe in each user's house or other safe place, and is connected to the outside world through wireless networks available in each city. Users retrieve their information accessing the Hub through hardware mobile devices (see Hardware paragraph).

Identity Fields (profile)

The Five Identity Fields (that contain infinite sub-categories) can be accessed, revised, and enriched with new data collected on the move while users pursue their daily activities, meet people, visit exhibition, and travel. The fields are:

Pragmatic (green) containing: business card, agenda, and meetings;

Cultural (orange) containing: interests, books, music, and travels;

Relational (purple) containing: friendships, family notes, events, experiences etc.

Emotional (red) containing: mood, feelings;

Governmental (blue) containing: credit cards, passport number, social security number, etc;

Taking into account the users daily experiences we extrapolated a chart (Figure 6) that relates day, time and kind of identity customers "use" while interacting with others. We can see a fairly public information Broadcasting of the user's Cultural, Relational, and Pragmatic

Identity while being in a business meeting during morning hours, and a more private Sharing of Cultural and Emotional Identity with closer friends during a dinner in the evening hours.

Figure 6, The chart shows the daytime and the kind of related personal information users share.

Through to this chart it has been possible to understand the different personal ways in which customers will have used the Identity Service in the future.

Identity Moods (communication)

The Five Identity Moods, that can be used to share Identity information, are:

Sharing: the mood in which specific presets of data can be delivered to a person or group of people: for example a document in a business meeting can be shared with everybody or only with a close collaborator.

Broadcasting: is the mood that delivers information to everybody without restraints, translating the user's Identity Information in any language of any country where the Identity Service is active: for example a researcher can broadcast his findings to the world.

Listening: for users that just want to listen to other users data, for voyeurs or lovers of stories, and culture hungry people.

ON/OFF: when On the users ask/allow the network to track and record events that are currently experienced, when Off incoming information are stored for a later review in the Identity Hub.

Identity Filters (management)

To avoid the risk of receiving unwanted information and enable customers to share safely their Identity Data the Identity Service and its partners established Identity Policies, a set of rules that protect the users and the exchange of information.

Trust and Safety Policy: control organisms such as non-governmental institutions will be established to survey regularly the Identity Service, its partnerships and alliances with banks and governmental entities.

Filters: users can apply many diverse filters to the information they receive in order to receive only the ones they need, such as anti-advertising filters and identity genre filters (Figure 7).

Figure 7, Personal information distribution: one to one, and one user to many.

Company filters: museums, companies, stores, partners of the Identity Service, will apply customer privacy filters for private meetings, for customers purchase history, and customers location in a certain day during a specific event.

Identity Donation: An Identity Donation partial or total can be decided by a user or his family after his death and become world heritage information (in case of a renown scientist's death for example).

Hardware

To share, retrieve, or collect new information the Identity Service Software runs on either mobile phones or PDAs or on the Wearable Identity (WeID).

Mobile phones and PDAs allow people to begin using the Identity Service with technologies currently on the market. The wearable Identity will be the future interface designed for a more seamless, elegant use in daily life.

The hardware itself is only the interface to access the data. In case of damage or loss of this device the data is safe in the Identity Hub and will repopulate a new device automatically. In case of a third party trying to use it, the SafeID software built into the Wearable Identity or Identity Enabled Mobile Phones will make the device freeze. Only the owner will be able to thaw it.

Identity Mobile Phones and PDAs

Because many mobile phones or PDAs come equipped with Java technology, storage space, and wireless data access, they provide the perfect mobile platform to springboard the Identity Service into the market.

Using a mobile phone the data could be viewed, listened to and read through the Identity Interface. Selecting the icons related to the chosen Identity Field, a menu appears showing the content.

Figure 8, Identity protocol Java screen interface on Sony Mobile Phone.

For Cultural Identity it shows a list of Books, Movies, Travels. The user selects the Field Priority (for example Books=1 and Movies=2) and then the content (example: Japanese Manga). The user selects the Mood (Figure 8) in which she wants to deliver this Cultural information for example Sharing (with a friend or many).

The interface will ask confirmation to start the user's data delivery. The interface will then animate with the color of the information Field shared and move at a speed given by the amount of information contained in it.

When receiving information by others the interface will add to the animation the color of the incoming information and change speed accordingly to the new amount of information. Clicking on the new color the user can read the information received and decide to store it or not in her Identity Hub. If Filters are applied users will not receive information of an undesired kind.

Wearable Identity

The Wearable Identity (Figure 9) is a tiny digital device containing a small amount of basic user information and an identification digital key (the user voice).

Figure 9, Wearable Identity components. Wearable Identity applied on a user’s garment.

Is composed by a pin (1) to be hooked in the user’s garments and a tiny headset/microphone (2) to be placed in the wearer’s ear. The WeID gives the customer the opportunity to recall a bigger amount of data contained in the Identity Hub at anytime in anyplace via voice-based commands. The WeID can be hooked on the user’s clothes, inside or outside, hidden or shown depending on the wearer’s mood.

Figure 10, How the Wearable Identity system works.

After the user whispers the Identity Fields and Moods into the WeID it starts to glow in the color shades of the Five Identity Fields, a color blinking faster highlights the amount of incoming information and the related Field. The features of the wearable interface (color, blinking, vibrating, or else) can be completely customized by users.

The auditory interface (Figure 10) will whisper the data received from other users into the wearer's ear thanks to the soft silicon headset, and before delivering the wearer's information to other users the interface will read it and after the user's confirmation proceed to deliver it in one of the Five Moods.

Why Voice-based Interfaces?

The ability to being heard producing and understanding spoken language is one of the prime accomplishments of our species. Including speech into a machine or being able to speak or input commands to an interface using our voice is a broadly significant step in enhancing telecommunication (Shedroff, 2003).

Why Wearable Digital Interfaces?

Clothing has always been the expression tool of our Identity. The ubiquitous flow of personal information will likewise craft our personal identities in the future. The wearable Identity responds to the users physical, emotional and communication needs while being a powerful

digital device. While clothing still offers protection for the body, the expressive function can be enhanced by technology.

Years ago thinking about a powerful computational technology hidden into a small pin would have been impossible, but today personal items that communicate are quickly becoming a reality. In Italy of about 60 million citizens, 58 million have a mobile phone; in Japan the Lovegety (Wired, 1998) brings together thousands of young lovers; with similar figures and projects the technology has built the basis for the desirability and diffusion of wearable digital interfaces.

In the future the identity devices will probably be implants and this will bring more social and moral issues than already highly advanced devices do, even if million people have implants such as IUD and pacemakers, it is still difficult to think about implants as a luxury rather than a medical device.

The role of jewelry and clothing had been to decorate and adorn but the choice made towards this end communicates Identity. While clothing undergoes seasonal trends, jewelry seems to be less ephemeral due to its emotional association. That's why the Wearable Identity is in a shape of a pin. The research showed that items such as pins and jewels are the natural fit for an interface based on personal identity sharing.

This contrasts somewhat with earlier models of wearable devices where scientists were proposing cyber suits featuring giant helmets and blinking lights – and people were concerned to start looking like Christmas trees. Identity Service hopes to rescue wearables from the scientists' geek-Dom and defines a new technology and fashion paradigm. A small pin hooked in people's clothes can represent a fashion statement, a way of perceiving technology and redefining its use, not only as a status symbol but also as a part of the body.

Analysis

Identity can be altered, shared, participated, through technology. Personal Identity is like a viral entity that can attack, conquer, and finally reside in another organism. Identity Service is intended as a platform to facilitate that kind of knowledge, identity, and perceptual transfer.

Risks of sharing

This system presents its risks as well, how can we be sure that people listening to our Identity are not going to steal it? Hackers will always be updated on how to steal what they need, privacy and freedom can be restricted by totalitarian regimes adopting the Identity Service as a citizen's actions control tool, people can receive from other customers unwanted information.

The goal of the Identity Service is to ease the flow of information between people, it isn't a centralized system and by leaving the control of information in the users hands it serves communication, presenting a similar risk to benefit ratio as other information networks like the Internet and the World Wide Web.

Conclusion and next steps

The Identity Service system was designed with the aspiration that it could encourage new social and cultural aspects in people's daily lives. The benefits could be: the disappearing of language and cultural boundaries, creation of new social dynamics and values, increasing of users' social life, self esteem and cultural heritage, knowledge sharing and development of new interests, enhance the sense of security and trust, increase of environmental sensitivity. Next user testing with a working Wearable Identity will provide insights whether any of these goals are legitimate possibilities.

In 3 to 5 years new communication technologies will be more powerful and better distributed (Wilson, 2003). Wi-Fi hotspots are growing in number every day, mobile phones allow us to surf the web, see movies, purchase bus tickets, count our steps and stay fit. New powerful microprocessors are inside every new device (making them effectively computers) and enabling users all around the world to be wirelessly connected with home or business, giving the possibility of reading e-mails and video-conferencing in a garden, probably being tracked by our own company or mobile service provider, while offering the invaluable freedom to move.

This data rich society that can be projected in the next 5 years, provides the ideal environment for the Identity Service to flourish. The only question that remains is whether we really want to know each other.

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